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What is a critical digital edition?

Centuries of scholarship, and many hundreds of editions, have made us familiar with critical editions in print form.¹ There might then appear to be an easy answer to the question posed by the title of this paper: a critical edition in digital form is just a translation of a critical edition in print form. Of course, we might discuss at length just what is meant by translation, but in essence the print and digital editions would have the same substance, expressed in different media.

In this paper, I propose that it is indeed true that there is a continuity between critical digital editions and printed critical editions. However, the continuity does not take a simple form, so that one could achieve a critical digital edition just by turning an existing printed edition into computer-readable files. Rather, I suggest that critical digital editions extend the paradigm of critical editing, in ways which demand a sharper sense of just what it is we do. I argue further that while the capacious freedoms of the digital medium might suggest that there is neither place nor need for “critical” editions in the new world, this perception is misplaced. Indeed, these very capacities mandate a critical attention to the tasks of evaluation and presentation even more than was the case for editors in the age of print. Critical editions and critical editors will be needed, and indeed may be valued as they were not in the print age.

One ought to begin with a firm definition of a printed critical edition. Here is our first difficulty: there is now no straight-forward consensus about just what is a critical edition in print form.² Forty years ago, it might have been possible to point at a single book and say: that is what a critical edition is and what it ought to be. An American might have taken one of the centenary Hawthorne volumes as an example; an Englishman, one of the Oxford Classical Texts series; a German, one of the Hölderlin

¹ A very early form of this paper was presented to the inaugural ESTS colloquium in Leicester in November 2000, under the title “So you think an electronic edition will solve all your problems”. Discussions at that colloquium, and especially the good fortune of being able to read the other contributions to this volume, reshaped that paper into this.

² See, as just a few of the many discussions around this subject, the essays collected in David Greetham *Scholarly Editing* (New York: Modern Language Association, 1995) and Greetham’s own *Theories of the Text* (Oxford: Clarendon, 1999); the writings of Jerome McGann (for example, “What is Critical Editing?” *Text* 5 (1991), 15-29); and of Peter Shillingsburg in, for example, *Scholarly Editing in the Computer Age: Theory and Practice* (Athens/ London: University of Georgia Press, 1986; second edition, Michigan: University of Michigan Press, 1996).

editions.³ Broadly: a critical edition “established” a text, presented that with an apparatus of variants, and surrounded text and apparatus with some account of the sources of the text and an explanation of the processes by which the text was established. There was considerable disagreement concerning these processes, and different opinions about the weights to be given to various kinds of source, and exactly how the text and apparatus should be presented, but the overall model held firm.

It does not hold now. In the past decades, two major developments in scholarly thinking about editorial theory have led to sharp questioning of this model. Firstly, the whole concept of “establishing the text” has been attacked.⁴ It is not at all clear what this phrase means, or exactly what “text” means in this context. The old confidence, that editors would make a single text and readers would accept it, has been shaken. Secondly, the rise of “bibliographic codes” and “sociological texts”, alongside increasing interest in the history of the book and studies in reception, have shown the poverty of a paradigm which detaches texts from the circumstances of their creation and the contexts of their publication and reception.⁵

These developments have led to something of a crisis in scholarly editing, at least among editors who think about what they do. Apparently, we should not aim to create a single authoritative text out of the many. But, what should we do instead? Apparently, our editions must offer a history of the text as object, showing its physical instantiations and transformations, revealing the agencies which shaped it. But how do we do this? Where is the boundary between an editor, and a historian of the whole world? The criticism has been sharpened by a growing sense of the inadequacy of the print medium to fulfil these visions of editorial responsibility. A book is excellent at presenting a single text; it is not so good at presenting many texts. And how could a book provide a full sense of the physical, sociological and historical circumstances of a text? A book might supply some photographs, and much commentary, but these seem hardly enough.

For editors who saw their work in terms of this set of problems, the advent of the new technology appeared as the answer to their dreams. Famously, with computers and hypertext, we need no longer present just one text. We can present two, a hundred, a

³ Hawthorne: Fredson Bowers et al (eds.) *The Centenary Edition of the Works of Nathaniel Hawthorne* (Columbus: Ohio UP, 1962-). Oxford: for example, E. J. Kenney’s edition of Ovid *Amores, Ars amatoria, Medicamina faciei femineae*, Oxford Classical Texts (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1961). Hölderlin, *Sämtliche Werke. Frankfurter Ausgabe* ed. D. E. Sattler (Frankfurt: Roter Stern: 1975-); and *Sämtliche Werke* [Große Stuttgarter Ausgabe] ed. Friedrich Beißner (Stuttgart : Cotta, 1943-1985).

⁴ Among notable assaults on the vanity of “definitive texts” are those of Shillingsburg, *Scholarly Editing in the Digital Age* (especially, editions of 19th century English and American authors) and David Parker (for biblical texts), *The Living Text of the Gospels* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press 1997).

⁵ These developments are usually associated with Jerome McGann (for example, *A Critique of Modern Textual Criticism* (Chicago: Chicago University Press, 1983)) and Donald McKenzie (for example, *Bibliography and the Sociology of Texts*, The Panizzi Lectures 1985 (London: British Library, 1986).

thousand. At a stroke, our first dilemma is solved. In place of editorial anxiety about which text, what choices, we can have all the texts, all the versions, and never have to make any decisions. It seems we may have a solution to our second dilemma too. We can have images, lots of images, showing all the different forms of the text, from manuscript scrawls, through cheap serialisations and deluxe printings. We can add galleries of sound, maps, videos: whole kits of material to equip the reader to taste the air the text breathed. What is more, this inclusive agenda, so in tune with an egalitarian age, seemed to offer all kinds of liberations: especially, the freedom from difficult choices. Making such an edition (to use, for the moment, the old term) is easy, at least in concept. Just gather images of all the texts. Just gather transcriptions of all the texts, linking them together. Add to this every kind of contextual material and we are done.

No wonder then, that some of the early writings on the marriage of textual scholarship and computing – my own included – are possessed of a kind of millennial enthusiasm.⁶ With one bound, we were free of all restrictions. We had found a golden path that would lead us into the glad confident morning of editorial utopia, where we editors would recapture our rightful value as the monarchs of the academy, the delphic dispensers of the editions of the future. As from nowhere, grandiose projects sprang up which aimed to gather in all the manuscripts or printed texts of this or that work, or author, or period. In some of these, the proposers aimed to surround the texts with massive collections of images, sound, maps, everything they could. Think, in no particular order, of the Perseus project, of the electronic *Piers Plowman*, the electronic *Beowulf*, the Blake Archive, the Book of the Duchess, my own Canterbury Tales Project, the Dante Gabriel Rossetti archive, the Early English Books Online initiative, and many other publications from what used to be Chadwyck-Healey, now part of ProQuest Information and Learning.⁷ And many, many more.

So, editorial thinkers wrote articles proclaiming the new world; funding agencies handed out large sums of money; publishers started up new divisions to handle the flood of electronic texts; prototypes rained upon us. A few actually got published. What, exactly, are these new electronic objects, on which so many of us have spent so much

⁶ See, for instance, the essays collected in George Landow and Paul Delaney (eds.) *The Digital Word: Text-based Computing in the Humanities* (Cambridge, Mass.: MIT, 1993); (somewhat more critically) in Kathryn Sutherland (ed.) *Electronic Text: Investigations in Method and Theory* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1997); and in Richard Finneran (ed.) *The Literary Text in the Digital Age* (Michigan: University of Michigan Press, 1996).

⁷ As well as web pages (a few of which are given below), CD-ROMs published by these projects include Robert Adams, Hoyt N. Duggan, Eric Eliason and Thorlac Turville-Peter (eds.) *Piers Plowman: MS 201 Corpus Christie College Oxford* (Michigan: Michigan University Press, 2000); Kevin Kiernan (ed.) *The Electronic Beowulf* (Michigan: Michigan University Press, 2000); Murray McGillivray (ed.) *Geoffrey Chaucer's Book of the Duchess: A Hypertext edition on CD-ROM* (Alberta: University of Calgary, 1997). Some Canterbury Tales Project publications are listed below.

time? Here, we find an interesting phenomenon: the people who made them seem unsure just what they have made. Several of these label themselves as “editions”, but all do with some kind of qualification. The most common of these qualifications is “hypertext edition”: thus, the Book of the Duchess, and many more (the Google search engine turns up “about 210,000” hits in response to this search and “about 5080” for the two words as a phrase). The William Blake archive appears to disclaim the tag “edition” and calls itself a “hypermedia archive”; similarly the Rossetti is a “hypermedia research archive”, and glosses this as a “hypertext instrument”. This reaching for terminology runs deep into these objects. While the title, “The Electronic Beowulf” is nicely non-committal, in the help files we are told that it is an “image-based edition”, without further explanation. Further on, we are told that the publication “includes a new edition” and shown a search screen which offers an “edition search” as distinct from a “transcript search”. A glance through the Blake Archive shows similar uncertainty. Overall, this is described as a “hypermedia archive”. But as you dig into it, you find that it does contain what it calls “illuminated books: an electronic edition”. Clicking on one of these brings us to what is now called an “electronic book”, and the first thing we see is not text, but image.

However, we do find a link to a transcription, and – as in so many places elsewhere – we find that the “electronic edition” defines itself as the transcriptions and the images together. Elsewhere, however (the Rossetti archive is a notable instance) the same combination is not described as an “edition”: often it is an archive, or an instrument, or an “electronic book”.

This uncertainty of terminology, this reluctance to use the term “edition”, is revealing. McGann’s seminal “Rationale of Hypertext” casts for an analogy for these new kinds of scholarly object, and finds it in the library.⁸ Like the library, his Rossetti archive is without boundaries, without a centre; it is a “archive of archives” (41-45). Like the library, it provides tools in the form of indices and cross-referencing. Like the library, it leaves the choice of how these tools should be used, and what should be read, and how it should be read, to the reader. The most complete instance of such a resource, of course, is the Perseus Project, which describes itself as a “digital library”.

“Digital library”; “hypertext instrument”; “hypermedia research archive”; “hypertext edition”; “electronic book”; “digital edition”: almost any phrase at all, except “critical edition”. Indeed, it might seem that the advent of the new technology has supplied the logical ending to the scholarly questioning of the critical editions over the last decades. Critical editing is dead. Instead we who used to be editors will become

⁸ Jerome McGann “The Rationale of Hypertext,” Sutherland (ed.) *Electronic Text* (see note 6), 19-46.

collectors of images, transcribers of texts (if indeed we are not able to have the texts read by computer, or transcribed in the Philippines), accumulators of these and other materials into something we might call by any of the names above. The answer to the question “what is a critical digital edition” is this: there is no such thing and there should be no such thing.

However, there is a small problem here. Consider further the analogy of the library. The library does not only contain manuscripts, facsimiles, catalogues. It contains books which help us evaluate these, which explain to us what these manuscripts and other primary texts are: which help us understand them, which help us read the text and texts they contain. A reader goes to a library to read, say, Blake, whom he or she has never read before. This reader sees on one shelf an edition of Blake; on another shelf, facsimiles of Blake manuscripts. Which does our reader choose first?⁹ Of course, we hope that the reader will question the text he or she reads, that he or she will be curious to see how the text appeared in the first manuscripts and print editions, and so will turn to the facsimiles, or will seek out museums containing Blake prints – or, will visit the Blake archive online. But few readers will begin with these; and even advanced readers, who have progressed deep into the manuscripts and into first and later print editions will wish, over and over, to see what others have thought of this manuscript or that, to examine this reading or that across all the tradition. The traditional printed critical edition supplied exactly these functions in the traditional print library. In the digital age, what agency will supply these functions? Or do we no longer need any such guidance? Are our readers now so skilled, so adept in these vast textual universes, that they can find their own pathways?

I believe that the vast new digital libraries of the future, in which – eventually – any reader anywhere will be able to access images of any manuscript, summon up sound and image from every epoch, will need exactly such objects, the digital counterpart of the traditional printed edition. Now, our reader of Blake is faced not just with the few facsimiles which the local library happens to own: this reader will have images of every page of every manuscript and every edition of Blake. Or (if we have our way), images of every manuscript and every early printed edition of the *Canterbury Tales*. Already, reviewers have asked, plaintively: what is a reader to do with all this? Where does one start reading? What should one read? What does “reading” mean, anyway, in such a universe of texts?

Some of these questions, at least, are exactly those which printed critical editions used to address. In the digital age, I submit, we need critical digital editions which take

on the same functions. Further, I suggest that the potential of the digital medium makes it possible for these critical digital editions to achieve cogency and immediacy far beyond their print predecessors. Well made critical digital editions might enrich the reading of many more people than have traditionally used such editions, and they might cover a range of materials much wider than the domain of the print edition.

Already, the ten years of experiment and development allow us to catch some glimpses of such critical digital editions. In what follows, I will present a series of propositions, in an attempt to map out the domain of critical digital editions. In the course of these propositions, I will refer particularly to two instances of critical digital editions. The first of these is comfortably familiar, in the sense that it is built on a well-established print model: the projected digital 28th edition of the Nestle-Aland Greek New Testament, itself the successor to 27 editions representing more than a hundred years of scholarship.¹⁰ A advanced prototype, illustrating the points I here make, is available at <http://nestlealand.uni-muenster.de>.¹¹ The second of these may be surprising, in that it is not an edition of a textual object at all: it is Martin Foys' digital edition of the Bayeux Tapestry, to be published on CD-ROM in early 2003.¹²

One can gain a sense of the parameters of these two editions from the following screen shots. First, from the digital Nestle-Aland:

⁹ Compare McGann "The Rationale of Hypertext" (see note 8) for a celebration of exactly this choice.

¹⁰ Barbara Aland, K. J. Karavidopoulos, C. M. Martini, Bruce Metzger (eds.) *Novum Testamentum Graece* (Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 1993). 27th Revised Edition. The first of this series of editions was edited by Eberhard Nestle, and appeared in 1898.

¹¹ This is a project funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, the Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, and the Münster Institut für neutestamentliche Textforschung. Full publication of the internet version and of a CD-ROM, to accompany the printed 28th edition, is scheduled for 2005. Screen shots here show the prototype internet version as at 9 September 2002. Errors such as the repeated οὐκ (after the addition in the Nestle-Aland text, and the lack of accents on that text, and rather many others) show its prototype status.

¹² Martin K. Foys (ed.) *The Bayeux Tapestry Digital Edition* (Leicester: Scholarly Digital Editions, forthcoming).

This view shows the opening screen for the “word by word” apparatus for the First Letter of John, chapter 1, verse 8. The top left gives the text, as it appears in the Nestle-Aland edition. Below this is the word by word apparatus for variants in the twenty-five manuscripts transcribed and collated in this edition. On the top right is the apparatus for the first verse as given in the printed Nestle-Aland. Notably, this records just one variant (the addition of *του θεου* before *ουκ*) while the collation on the left shows several other variants not recorded in the printed apparatus. Each of the witness sigils in the collation is linked to a full transcript of the manuscript, showing the text in the manuscript both by chapter and by page. On the bottom right are two instructions: move the mouse over, or click on, a word in the verse. The next screen shows what happens when you do this:

Two new windows have appeared. The top one appears when the mouse moves over *αλνθεια*, just before the addition. The bottom one appears when the mouse clicks on the word *ουκ*, just after the addition. In both cases, we see first a list of all the transcribed and collated witnesses which agree with the base text (a “positive apparatus”) followed by the variants on the word itself (there are none on *αλνθεια*) and the witnesses which do not have this verse. The difference is that the contents of the top window change as the mouse moves over a word; the bottom one only changes when you click on a word. This is designed to allow the reader to compare the full apparatus on any two words, while keeping in view the text of the whole verse and the summary apparatus on the left and in the top right. Finally, note that the toolbar at the top of the window allows you to navigate very rapidly to any other part of the New Testament, and choose how you want to see this (whether in apparatus, or manuscript transcript).

Second, from Martin Foys’ *Bayeux Tapestry Digital Edition*:

The top of the window gives a translation of the Latin text contained in the Tapestry. Below is an image of part of the Tapestry, focussing on what Foys labels as panel 59: the crucial (and controversial) oath of Harold to William. The whole Tapestry is presented as

a single scrolling panel, so that one can see the previous or next scene just by clicking in the panel at either edge. Alternatively, one can click in the navigation outline below the Tapestry, and move straight to that point. Below this, is Foys' commentary on this scene. First, he relates the correspondences between the Tapestry's depiction of this scene and the accounts in other primary sources. Translations of all these are presented on the CD-ROM, with links to them in the "Library" section. Then, Foys summarizes the major scholarly discussions of this scene, and explains the significance of this scene in the whole Tapestry. Below this commentary there is a line of icons. "Tools" offers searching and slide-show facilities. "Background" gives access to translations of primary sources, maps, images of related objects, glossary, introductions, and bibliography. "Facsimiles" presents full image records of three facsimiles of the Tapestry, dating from the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries. Other icons switch commentary and translation views on and off, and permit navigation by panel and scene.

In their different ways, and to different degrees, these two critical digital editions (and others I will mention parenthetically) illustrate the propositions I here present. Note that neither of these two embodies all these propositions, and indeed it is likely that few editions ever will. The propositions are, as it were, co-ordinates by which critical digital editions might be located.

1. A critical digital edition is anchored in a historical analysis of the materials

At least since Griesbach's work on the New Testament, scholarly editing has sought to locate the texts it edits in a historical relation: this sequence of authorial manuscripts, this reading giving rise to that, this text printed at this point in time.¹³ One does not have to see texts in this light: one could see them as related thematically, or not related at all. There are also degrees of historical relation: between the rigidity of strict stemmatics, through the looser models of relative contemporaneity implicit in many editions of manuscript texts, to the precise chronology of authorial manuscript and first and later printings. However, the starting point of critical editing is the conviction that the text came into existence at some point, even if we are unable to locate this precisely, and that its transformations occurred at discrete intervals, even if we cannot locate or order these

¹³ Johann Jakob Griesbach (ed.) *Novum Testamentum Graece*. 2nd ed. Halle, 1796. On Griesbach and his influence see Bruce M. Metzger, *The Text of the New Testament: its Transmission, Corruption and Restoration* (New York/Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1992). Naturally, there had been historical observations on aspects of textual traditions before Griesbach (see the discussions in L. D. Reynolds and N. G. Wilson (eds.) *Scribes and Scholars: A Guide to the Transmission of Greek and Latin Literature* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1991). However Griesbach appears to have been the first to have attempted a historical categorisation of an entire textual tradition.

certainly. As Bowers puts it, with typical confidence, our business is “the determination of the exact forms of the early documents in which the text is preserved and of the facts about their relationship to one another.”¹⁴

By contrast, the hypertext archive may make no assertions about historical relations. The various forms of a text float past each other in hyperspace, like ships which pass in the night. Nor is there usually any attempt at comparison of the different forms of the text, of the kind instanced in the Nestle-Aland example. How close are the different texts? Are they close at all? Do the differences amount to revision, distinct versions, or even a quite different text? Up to now, electronic publications have commonly paid little attention to such questions. The texts are simply “there”: but quite where “there” is, or how they came “there”, are questions which might not even be asked, let alone answered.

2. A critical digital edition presents hypotheses about creation and change

A view of texts as objects in time and space leads naturally to attempts, by whatever means and using whatever evidence is available, to illuminate the circumstances of the creation of the text and of all its transformations. The traditional concentration of editors on texts written centuries or millennia ago means that often we are so distant from the circumstances of their creation that scholars perforce must concentrate on the variance within the extant (and perhaps much later) documents: thus the Bible, all classical texts, almost all medieval texts and most renaissance texts. But for the modern era we do have material, often in vast amounts, and it is reasonably the task of editors to sift this, and to use it to clarify the stages of the evolving text. Thus Foys thoroughly evaluates the evidence for the date and origin of the Bayeux Tapestry. Similarly, Briggs’ account of the making of Mirlees’ *Paris 1919* illustrates how critical judgement might be applied to the elucidation of the making of a text printed once and only once in the author’s lifetime, and so almost completely without variants.

Naturally, the making of hypotheses requires the making of judgements: this reading as more likely to be ancestral than that; this manuscript as presenting a likely earlier stage than that; this change is more probably authorial than scribal. It is a depressing truth that in the early years of electronic books many scholars who showed great distinction of judgement in the making of print editions have spent much more time accumulating materials and negotiating all the problems thrown up by a new mode of publication than thinking about the texts they are studying. It is also depressingly true, that the massive

¹⁴ Fredson Bowers, “Some Principles for Scholarly Editions,” *Art and Error* eds. R. Gottesman and S. Bennett (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 1970), 55.

volume of material (all the *Canterbury Tales*!) can seduce the editor into considering sheer effort its own reward: readers should be grateful just to have so much, and should not expect that editors think as well. One hopes that this flight from judgement is temporary. It will need to be. To make sense of so much requires a constant cycle of considered experiment and revision. And if we editors, who are privileged to spend so much time with the texts we edit, cannot or will not make sense of them, how can we expect our readers to do so?

3. *A critical digital edition supplies a record and classification of difference over time, in many dimensions and in appropriate detail*

It is one matter just to present different forms of a text. It is quite another to show just how different they are: to discover the differences, to quantify and classify them, to find patterns in the peaks and troughs of similarity and difference. To do this requires meticulous collation, built on the most accurate record of the text. Here indeed, the digital medium offers opportunities beyond those available in the print medium. No more do we have to consign the variants to unreadable apparatus, from which the exact sequence of readings in any one text may be extracted only with difficulty (if at all). No more do we have to filter our apparatus rigorously, omitting many variants simply because the publisher will not or cannot print all that we might like. No more do we have to confine ourselves to selective collation, marking them on cards or sheets of paper and having, at every point, to decide – is this a variant or is it not? Now, we may transcribe the texts in full and collate them by computer. We can show the entire collation, without limit, if we wish. This can be seen in the Nestle-Aland example, where the computer collation on the left shows several variants not present in the print apparatus reproduced on the top right. Further, in the second Nestle-Aland screen we can give an explicit positive apparatus, declaring exactly what witnesses support the Nestle-Aland text – an operation rather difficult to deduce from the print apparatus. And, we can include the full transcripts of the witnesses collated, and include links from the collation (as in the Nestle-Aland) to the transcripts themselves. In a different mode, the Foys edition presents difference over time in the inclusion of full digitizations of the three major facsimiles of the Tapestry made in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, alongside representations of the Tapestry as it might have appeared (say) when hung in Bayeux cathedral, or in a medieval feast hall.

In the case of textual change, once we have gathered all this information, we can use yet further computer tools to analyse the patterns of variation. One of the most remarkable developments in textual scholarship and computing in the last decade has

been the demonstration that phylogenetic methods, used for the creation of genetic hypothesis concerning the relations of species (formally, “taxa”) by analysis of the characteristics they share and do not share, can give considerable help to scholars seeking to unravel the stages of evolution of a textual tradition.¹⁵ In turn, this has fostered a new confidence in some of us, at least, that such genetic analyses can be useful in illuminating individual readings in the texts we study, a development I have elsewhere called the “New Stemmatics.”¹⁶

These new possibilities are not without their own problems. The sheer ease of electronic publication can encourage its own brand of intellectual laziness. Certainly we can print all the transcripts, and every word of the collation. Certainly we can make a collation just by throwing a switch, and we can create phylogenetic tables which look just like traditional stemmata by throwing another switch. But should we? Jerome McGann is fond of citing William Morris on the need for “resistance in the materials.”¹⁷ Here the problem is lack of resistance. We do not have to make choices; choices are difficult; so the temptation is not to make them. Instead, we might just dump all the information into the electronic edition and let the reader try to make sense of it. We can even congratulate ourselves, as we do this, on our obedience to fashionable theories about “empowering” the reader, and achieving profoundly “decentred”, “un-edited” texts, and see our action not as abdication of responsibility but as a principled refusal to play the patriarchal, authoritarian editor. Whose fault is it, then, when readers find these massive archives of unordered information overwhelming and unusable?¹⁸

The key word in the proposition is “appropriate”. What is “appropriate” to include in our transcriptions, in the collations, in the analyses; how do we best employ what we discover? The computer seems to suggest that we are free from having to make any such decisions. In fact, this illusion of freedom from choice is itself precisely the “resistance in the materials” against which we have to build our critical digital editions. Even transcription, apparently a simple act of representing letter by letter what is before us in the source document, is not so simple at all. Do we record the “bibliographic codes” as we transcribe; if so, how? Do we aim at a regularised-spelling, or a graphemic, or a

¹⁵ For example, A. C. Barbrook, N. F. Blake, C. J. Howe, P. M. W. Robinson (eds.) “The Phylogeny of *The Canterbury Tales*,” *Nature* 394 (1998), 839; and in my “Analysis Workshop” and “Stemmatic Commentary” sections in E. Solopova (ed.) *The General Prologue on CD-ROM*. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2000). For a contrary view, see Neil Cartlidge, “The *Canterbury Tales* and Cladistics,” *Neuphilologische Mitteilungen* 1999, 135-150.

¹⁶ Robinson, “Analysis Workshop” (see note 15).

¹⁷ For example, in “The Rationale of Hypertext” (see note 8), 19.

¹⁸ An extreme example of this attitude was the scholar who seriously suggested to me that he would use optical character reading to create computer reader files, and then employ a collation program to collate these files, and then present transcripts and collations as an “electronic edition”, all without a human editor having to read a single word. He seemed puzzled at my lack of enthusiasm for this project.

graphetic transcript? Would we (a simple case) record an instance where the typesetter has used an upside down “u” to represent “n” – and how would we record this? Do we record marginalia, glosses, doodlings, other markings? Then we have the collation itself. Do we just let the computer run along on its own, and take whatever it gives us? Or do we intervene at almost every word, regularising according to our sense of what is significant, adjusting the sequence of variation to make as clear as we can what we think is happening? All this requires thought, method, and decision.

4. A critical digital edition may present an edited text, among all the texts it offers

A starting point of many discussions of electronic texts is a celebration of the freedom they offer from the old model of the single text plus apparatus. Instead, we have all the texts. We do not have to present an edited text, whether “eclectic” or “best text”.

In some cases, indeed, it might be appropriate not to supply such a text. But there are many circumstances – perhaps, even the majority of circumstances – where it will be appropriate to privilege one text (which might be an editorial construct, or a particular text among the many included) above others. I have discussed this elsewhere,¹⁹ where I assert that this does not mean anything like a return to the days of the “definitive” or “authoritative” text. I suggest there that a powerful reason to construct a new text, which is then placed at the centre of the entire edition, is that such a text is that which best explains all the extant documents.

Indeed, this seems the most fruitful way to consider the text given in the top left of the Nestle-Aland screens, which is the text of the Nestle-Aland edition itself. It would be perilous indeed to assert that this text is word-for-word identical with a presumed first century original. But the value of this text does not arise from its place as the endpoint of the editor’s work, as the achieved and definitive reconstruction of the text as it may have existed at the moment of its composition – an assertion which we could never test, even if we were so foolish as to make it. It has a different, less ambitious, but arguably more real value. It should be seen as the best starting point for the reader’s own explorations of the text. If you should wish to discover the different forms the text of the New Testament took in the millennia of its history (and every interested reader should wish this): here is the best place to begin.

I have suggested that we might similarly wish to present just such a text of the *Canterbury Tales* (“The One Text”). Recent work on Caxton’s second edition of the

¹⁹ P. M. W. Robinson, “The One Text and the Many Texts”, *Literary and Linguistic Computing* 15:1 (2000), 5-14.

Tales has revealed several points at which both the manuscripts most usually regarded as authoritative for the *Tales*, the Ellesmere and Hengwrt manuscripts, actually agree in what appears to be scribal error, and the reading most likely to have stood in the archetype of the whole tradition is preserved in other witnesses.²⁰ Presenting a single text, containing these readings in preference to those usually given, would remind readers that all extant texts are fallible. Secondly, the arguments presented in favour of the changes we make will vary in substance and force: this will suggest to the reader that editors too are fallible, that this text too is fallible. Presenting this text at the centre of the edition would say to readers: here is a clearly defined route into all the texts; start here. But all the rhetoric of the edition, the collations and other transcripts which will crowd upon the reader even as the mouse moves over the text (as in the second Nestle–Aland screen) will say to the reader: this is one text among many. You may start here, but you certainly should not finish here.

5. *A critical digital edition allows space and tools for readers to develop their own hypotheses and ways of reading*

To apply the critical arts and sciences to editing in the electronic domain is not to return to the days when an editor established and printed a text and said, effectively: take it or leave it. There is no excuse, in the digital world, for an edition which does not make available every stage of the material and all the processes behind its making. Further, these should be so presented as to allow the reader to test what the editor has done, and to develop their own counter-hypotheses and ways of seeing the text. In its simplest form this might be just a “slide show” tool, as in the Foys edition, allowing the reader to build and replay useful pathways through the edition. More ambitiously, the *General Prologue on CD-ROM* included phylogenetic and other analytic tools, together with elaborate instructions and full data sets for their use. Still more ambitiously, the digital Nestle Aland and later *Canterbury Tales* publications propose to make the collation tool itself available online. One could then build one’s own views of the multiple texts, selecting (for example) a different base, or choosing to see the collation with different levels of regularisation.

Perhaps the largest shift which has taken place in my own work on the *Canterbury Tales* is the change of aim I signalled in the “General Editors’ Introduction”

²⁰ B. Bordalejo *The manuscript source of Chaucer’s second edition of the Canterbury Tales and its place in the textual tradition of the Tales* (Doctoral thesis in progress, De Montfort University, Leicester UK).

to the *General Prologue*, when remarking on the differences between our earlier Wife of Bath's Prologue CD-ROM and the General Prologue CD-ROM:²¹

...the aim of The Wife of Bath's Prologue CD-ROM was to help editors edit; our aim now is also to help readers read.

To put this another way, as editors we do not seek only to practise the critical arts and sciences ourselves: we seek to help our readers practise them also. By pointing out (for example) points where our edited text of the *Canterbury Tales* differs from that found in the manuscripts used for over a hundred years as the base of the text, we invite readers to question further. We might be rather conservative, in choosing only to replace readings where we think these manuscripts are in error. Our readers might wish to be more adventurous: to suppose (as is indeed possible) that there existed an early archetype which differed rather more from the Hengwrt and Ellesmere manuscripts than they differ from each other, and whose readings are typically found (for instance) in the Caxton second edition and in a handful of manuscripts. We will offer the tools to identify what these readings might be and to explore this possibility further.

6. *A critical digital edition must offer all this in a manner which enriches reading*

One could replace the earlier five propositions by this single dictate. The aim of all our work is expressed in this one proposal. It is far from evident that the simple multiplication of images and texts in a "hypermedia archive" enriches reading at all. Indeed, the reverse is likely to be true: it reduces texts to dissonant noises. It is also the case that the breathtaking advances in computer technology in just ten years have now made it possible (but not yet easy!) for scholars to present all this in an attractive and accessible fashion. The Foys edition is an outstanding example of this. Foys himself has a background in graphic design, and he enlisted talented graphic designers to create a visually pleasing ensemble of colour, image, text and icon, with a consistent interface across the many parts of the edition. Further, one may move to any part of the Tapestry itself by a single click on the "outline" below the Tapestry images, or move to any of the associated images and materials by no more than three clicks through the icons at the base of the screen.

²¹ P. M. W. Robinson, *The Wife of Bath's Prologue on CD-ROM* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1996); 'G

The Nestle-Aland digital edition screens show a similar effort, to open out the information on variation contained in the notoriously compressed printed apparatus so that what is happening in each verse is as clear as possible. For example: a classic difficulty when viewing a text and apparatus is seeing exactly what words in the text correspond with what words in the apparatus. In the Nestle-Aland screen, the apparatus at the bottom left tells us that there is a variant on ἐχόμεν. In a long verse, it might be difficult to see exactly where this word is in the edited text, especially if the word occurs at several places. The interface solves this problem neatly. When the mouse passes over the lemma ἐχόμεν in the apparatus, the matching word in the edited text turns red.

We have only just begun to exploit the possibilities that the new media offers us now, let alone those to come. We can imagine layering of information, using something like a three-dimensional presentation of variation; animation of texts, with one text “morphing” into another, and more. These and other tools will come, and we should use them where and when they give the most dramatic expression to the texts we offer. For instance: a genetic edition might show the author’s text actually growing on the page, presenting the series of additions, deletions, alterations in the “avant-texte” one after another, as if it was being written as we watch.²²

It is striking, that each of the six propositions I here set out could be applied, without any change of wording at all, to critical editions in print form. There is a real continuity between our work as editors in the digital age and that of our predecessors. All of us are engaged in attempting to understand what we are editing, and then trying to communicate what we have learnt. It is revealing, however, that I find myself having to explain this at all: what should be self-evident seems to have been overlooked in the rush to exploit the power of the computer to accumulate material. To understand what we have gathered, and to help others understand it, are rather difficult. But such understanding is exactly what critical digital editions might achieve and foster – so long as we are prepared to make the effort.

Effort, there certainly is. Foys spent much of ten years gathering the material behind his edition, working out how best to present it, experimenting with different arrangements of image and text. An array of complex processes underlie the Nestle-Aland text: painstakingly-encoded transcripts, rigorously-adjusted computer collations,

²² Daniel Ferrer demonstrated a *Finnegans Wake* hypertext with exactly this feature at the Society for Textual Scholarship conference in New York in 1993. Compare Gabler’s account of Joyce’s writing of one page from the Circe notebook in this volume.

meticulous attention to detail throughout. At present, it is certainly a difficulty that the level of skill and commitment required to make such editions is currently available only to the most determined individuals or to the best-resourced editorial teams. We can expect that as the tools mature, and as pioneer projects clear the way for others, it will become progressively easier to make such editions.

Great effort certainly; but possibly, also, great rewards. It is a commonplace of commentary on computers and the humanities that the computer makes certain kinds of reading more difficult.²³ This is, decisively, not the case for critical editions in digital form. I have said that each of the six propositions is true of both print and digital critical editions. But in each of these six cases, computer methods may allow us to understand rather more, and especially communicate far more of what we understand, than could ever be the case for print editions. As perhaps nowhere else in the humanities, computer methods may reinforce and extend the best of what we do: to think critically, and to help others think critically.

²³ Thus, the shibboleth “you cannot read a book on a computer in bed” (or in a bath, or on the beach). In more extreme form, Sven Birkerts (*The Gutenberg Elegies* (New York: Fawcett Columbine 1994)) argues that the very act of using computers “leaches out traditional meaning and a sense of self” (219) and disconnects us from “the deep time we thrive in: the time of history, tradition, ritual, art, and true communion” (229).